

Modelling of oxydibenzenesulfonyl hydrazide (OBSh) in gas-phase

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Oxydibenzenesulfonyl hydrazide (OBSh), under some circumstances, can act as a foaming factor, and also as a crosslinking agent in the hardening reaction. Another use of OBSh is elastomer production under room pressure, such as natural rubber, styrene-butadiene rubber, or neoprene; and also in the solidifying reaction of thermoplastic production such as, acrylonitrile butadiene styrene plastics, polyethylene, polystyrene, or polyvinylchloride, and can also be used together with the combinations of resin and rubber. It has considerable advantages in wire and cable production due to its isolatable characteristics. The structural and physical features of OBSh were calculated using the quantum chemical calculations of Density Functional Theory (DFT). The analysis was carried out on the possible reaction path of OBSh molecule with OH radicals. Gauss View 5 and the Gaussian 09 programs were used for the calculation of optimized geometry and the geometric optimization for the determination of the lowest energy status. For the gas phase, activation energy for the estimated reaction paths was calculated and their most stable state from the thermodynamic perspective was determined. The aim of this study is to estimate the degradation mechanism of OBSh molecule in gas phase.

Keywords: OBSh, DFT, Gaussian 09, hydroxyl radical.

Introduction

Oxydibenzenesulfonyl hydrazide (OBSh), which is known with its chemical formula as $C_{12}H_{14}N_4O_5S_2$, is a colourless, crystalline solid foaming agent used for rubber and plastic and also as a polymer additive, and is known to be denser than water. Direct contact with OBSh may cause to irritation on skin, in eyes, or mucous membranes. Due to its being a toxic gas, OBSh affects people negatively when this chemical is inhaled. OBSh, which is used as the foaming agent, decomposes exothermically and releases nonpolar oligomers, N, and H_2O , in its foaming process^{1,2}.

Hydrazine derivatives, which also are available in some plants, have a widespread use in industry, agriculture and medicine. In scientific literature, there are many studies, which reveal that some hydrazine derivatives were found out to be potentially carcinogenic in animals, especially in mice. Nevertheless, studies on the potential carcinogenicity in mammalian cells have not been completed yet³.

OBSh is an organic compound. As stated in many studies, organic contaminants are known to exist in water at very low concentrations. Thus, it is crucial that drinking water be purified from the organic contaminants. Solar light on earth helps water systems like lakes, rivers, etc. to be purified naturally. Large organic molecules are degraded into smaller basic molecules through sunbeams, and finally form CO_2 , H_2O , other small molecules⁴⁻⁶. Organic compounds react with OH radical by undergoing photolysis, and this reaction is the most dominant reaction among dissipation reactions in the atmosphere. Biomolecules, which are hydroxyl scavengers at various speeds, are specific detectors for hydroxyl radical due to their ability of hydroxylation. Moreover, the repulsion of existent substituents, and the electron withdrawal lead to the position of the attack to the ring. The attack of any hydroxyl radical to an aromatic compound leads to a hydroxylated product to be formed, and these newly formed products may be much more harmful than their original product in the beginning of the process, thus it is essential that these

products be monitored^{6,7-9}.

In this study, the kinetics of the degradation reaction path of O molecule with OH radical was analysed theoretically through the density functional theory (DFT) method. Theoretical calculations were carried out at DFT/B3LYP/631G(d) level in gas-phase¹⁰.

Computational models:

Mean bond distances and geometric parameters of the closed ring were used to form molecule models. Tetrahedral angles were used for the sp³-hybridized carbon and oxygen atoms and 120° for the sp²-hybridized carbon atoms was used in the computational modelling. The aromatic ring was left planar, excluding the position of attack. Since there was an alteration in the hybridization state of the carbon at the addition centre from sp² to sp³, the attacking OH radical was estimated to form a tetrahedral angle with the C-H bond^{6,11}.

Molecular orbital calculations:

In photocatalytic degradation reactions of O molecule, it is possible that products more harmful than those in the original material could be formed. For this reason, it is crucial to apprehend the nature of the primary intermediate products before conducting a photocatalytic degradation reaction experimentally. Calculations carried out by quantum mechanical methods provide the most reliable and precise information. Hence, due to the yield produced being the same, photocatalytic degradation reactions of O molecule and its hydroxy derivatives were based on the direct reaction of these molecules with OH radical. With this aim, the kinetics of the reactions of O molecule with OH radical was theoretically analysed. The study was initiated with O molecule and then exposed to reaction with OH radical and the reaction yields were modelled in gas-phase. Experimental results in the scientific literature revealed that OH radical detaches a hydrogen atom from saturated hydrocarbons, and OH radical is added to unsaturated hydrocarbons and materials with this structure^{6,12,13}. Therefore, possible reaction paths for the analysed reactions were calculated. In this study, primarily the conformation analyses of the foaming agent OBSH were conducted, and the conformers with the lowest energy, or in other words, the most stable ones were determined. Geometric optimizations of the molecule were carried out at DFT/

B3LYP/6-31G(d) level. As a result of the quantum chemical calculations, the geometric parameters, energy, enthalpy, and Gibbs-free energy, and also load density, and mulliken loads in gas-phase were determined^{6,10}.

Methodology:

The investigated reaction system was composed of OH radical, which are open-shell species. It is known that open-shell molecules cause severe problems in quantum mechanical calculations. The self-consistent field method (SCF) calculation will proceed for an open-shell case in the same way as for a closed-shell case. Nevertheless, because of two sets of equations having to be dealt with, at each iteration, the program has to consider, either simultaneously or successively, the closed-shell and the open-shell equations. In this respect, the computational burden could be two-times larger for an open shell than that for a closed-shell. Another point raised in connection with the optimization of the SCF process for open-shell molecules is the relative intricacy of the sequence of calculations for the closed-shell Hamiltonian and the open-shell Hamiltonian¹⁴.

DFT methods, taking the electron correlation into account, use the precise electron density to calculate molecular properties and energies. Spin contamination does not affect them and hence, for calculations involving open-shell systems, they become favourable. DFT calculations were made by the hybrid B3LYP functional combining the HF and Becke exchange terms with the Lee-Yang-Parr correlation functional. In such calculations, it is the 6-31G(d) basis set that is used^{6,10}.

Results and discussion

According to Fig. 1 of O molecule, O₃, O₃₂, N₃₃ and N₃₅ molecules on the right, O₂₃, O₂₄, N₂₅ and N₂₇ molecules on the left, and O₁₁. When bond angles and bond lengths were investigated, values written bold in Table 1 gave preliminary information about the fragmentation sites of the molecule.

Bond lengths and bond angles of O molecule, which is analysed in this study, and its three stable fragments namely, O₁, O₂ and O₃ are given in this table. The bond lengths and angles with the highest value are bold written in this table. The probable stable fragmentation pathway of O molecule is given in Fig. 2.

Fig. 1. Optimized figures of O molecule (yellow, sulphur; blue, nitrogen; white, hydrogen; red, oxygen; grey, carbon).

Table 1. Bond lengths and angles of some stable fragments of O molecule

O	Bond length (Å)	O	Bond angle (°)	O1	Bond length (Å)	O1	Bond angle (°)
N ₃₃ N ₃₅	1.41245	N ₃₅ N ₃₃ S ₃₀	112.06538	N ₂₅ S ₂₂	1.70068	N ₃₂ N ₃₀ S ₂₇	112.06146
S ₃₀ N ₃₃	1.71834	N ₃₃ S ₃₀ O ₃₁	103.40508	N ₃₂ N ₃₀	1.41248	C ₁₉ S ₂₇ O ₂₈	109.69545
S ₃₀ O ₃₁	1.46640	N ₃₃ S ₃₀ O ₃₂	110.36653	N ₃₀ S ₂₇	1.71806	C ₁₉ S ₂₇ O ₂₉	108.13353
S ₃₀ C ₁₉	1.78407	O ₃₂ S ₃₀ C ₁₉	108.14411	S ₂₂ C ₁	1.78899	N ₃₀ S ₂₇ O ₂₉	110.38744
C ₁₂ O ₁₁	1.37797	O ₃₁ S ₃₀ C ₁₉	109.70571	S ₂₂ O ₂₄	1.46620	N ₃₀ S ₂₇ O ₂₈	103.40950
C ₄ O ₁₁	1.37748	O ₃₁ S ₃₀ C ₁₉	109.70571	S ₂₂ O ₂₃	1.46624	C ₁ S ₂₂ O ₂₄	107.54988
N ₂₅ N ₂₇	1.41250	C ₄ O ₁₁ C ₁₂	121.68182	S ₂₇ O ₂₈	1.46637	C ₁ S ₂₂ O ₂₃	107.68583
N ₂₅ S ₂₂	1.71876	N ₂₇ N ₂₅ S ₂₂	111.99521	S ₂₇ O ₂₉	1.46694	C ₄ O ₁₁ C ₁₂	121.70423
S ₂₂ C ₁	1.78372	N ₂₅ S ₂₂ O ₂₃	103.39603	S ₂₇ N ₁₉	1.78432	O ₂₈ S ₂₇ O ₂₉	121.15952
O2	Bond length (Å)	O ₃₁ S ₃₀ C ₁₉	109.70571	O3	Bond length (Å)	O ₂₃ S ₂₂ O ₂₄	122.52825
S ₃₀ C ₁₉	1.78564	N ₂₇ N ₂₅ S ₂₂	112.07913	S ₂₇ N ₃₀	1.71000	O ₂₈ S ₂₇ N ₃₀	109.47122
S ₂₂ N ₂₅	1.71730	O ₃₁ S ₃₀ O ₃₂	122.69507	S ₂₇ C ₁₉	1.78000	O ₂₉ S ₂₇ N ₃₀	109.47122
N ₂₅ N ₂₇	1.41252	O ₂₃ S ₂₂ O ₂₄	121.21582	O ₁₁ C ₁₂	1.43000	N ₂₅ S ₂₂ C ₁	109.47120
C ₁ S ₂₂	1.78613	C ₄ O ₁₁ C ₁₂	121.63381	S ₂₂ C ₁	1.78000	C ₁ S ₂₂ O ₂₃	109.47123

When Mulliken loads of O molecule given in Table 2 were analysed. Mulliken loads of the studied O molecule and all its fragments are given in this table. The atoms with the highest electronegativity are bold written in the table. For example,

N₂₇ and N₃₅ are atoms with the highest electronegativity among all atoms with high electronegativity, and are marked as red in this Table 2.

Energy values in gas phase of the O molecule and its all

Fig. 2. Probable fragmentation paths of O molecule.

Table 2. Mulliken loads of studied fragments

O	O1	O2	O3	O4
O₁₁ -0.564521	O₁₁ -0.564373	O₁₁ -0.562860	O₁₁ -0.564411	O₁₁ -0.562827
O₂₃ -0.545626	O₂₃ -0.536879	O₂₃ -0.543170	O₂₃ -0.531019	O₂₃ -0.536132
O₂₄ -0.532863	O₂₄ -0.533034	O ₂₄ -0.531937	O₂₄ -0.537824	O₂₄ -0.529870
N₂₅ -0.564232	N ₂₅ -0.815162	N₂₅ -0.565390	N ₂₅ -0.815634	N ₂₅ -0.815872
N ₂₇ -0.590464	S ₂₇ 1.230531	N ₂₇ -0.590923	S ₂₇ 1.169158	S ₂₇ 0.946383
O₃₁ -0.544736	O₂₈ -0.544662	S ₃₀ 0.946117	O₂₈ -0.531729	O₂₈ -0.511515
O₃₂ -0.533611	O₂₉ -0.533215	O₃₁ -0.513078	O₂₉ -0.537027	O₂₉ -0.512390
N₃₃ -0.564726	N₃₀ -0.564920	O₃₂ -0.511715	N ₃₀ -0.815662	
N ₃₅ -0.590546	N₃₂ -0.590550			
O5	O6	O7	O8	O9
O₁₁ -0.569297	O ₁₁ -0.560980	O₁₁ -0.568111	O ₁₁ -0.567470	O₁₁ -0.568483
O₂₂ -0.545007	O₂₃ -0.510881	O₂₂ -0.543656	O₂₃ -0.543686	O ₂₃ -0.549720
O₂₄ -0.547326	O₂₄ -0.509895	O₂₄ -0.530918	S ₂₄ 0.943833	S ₂₄ 0.509497
O₂₅ -0.536001	S ₂₅ 0.948051	O₂₅ -0.541531	O₂₅ -0.514614	O ₂₅ -0.543899
N₂₆ -0.564121	O₂₆ -0.509899	N ₂₆ -0.815581	O₂₆ -0.514906	
N ₂₈ -0.589968	O₂₇ -0.510884	S ₂₈ 0.509536		

O10	O11	O12	O13	O14
O ₁₁ -0.568989	O₁₁ -0.576329	O₁₁ -0.575676	O₁₁ -0.575569	O₁ -0.664287
S ₂₂ -0.013311	S ₂₂ -0.030737	S ₂₂ -0.030487		
O₂₄ -0.515220				
O₂₅ -0.514728				

Table 3. Gibbs-free energy, enthalpy, and energy values (au) for the gas- phase of the degraded fragments of the O molecule

Gas	O	O1	O2	O3
ΔE (au)	-1856.687437	-1801.392479	-1746.043727	-1746.097532
ΔH (au)	-1856.686493	-1801.391535	-1746.042783	-1746.096588
ΔG (au)	-1856.763831	-1801.467134	-1746.114375	-1746.170572
	O4	O5	O6	O7
ΔE (au)	-1690.748730	-1671.897266	-1635.399688	-1616.602235
ΔH (au)	-1690.747786	-1671.896322	-1635.398744	-1616.601291
ΔG (au)	-1690.817239	-1671.967109	-1635.464691	-1616.670739
	O8	O9	O10	O11
ΔE (au)	-1561.254076	-1487.111509	-1485.043581	-1334.684513
ΔH (au)	-1561.253132	-1487.110565	-1485.042637	-1334.683569
ΔG (au)	-1561.318145	-1487.174532	-1485.104846	-1334.742610
	O12	O13	O14	O15
ΔE (au)	-936.500865	-538.317189	-307.349412	-232.143520
ΔH (au)	-936.499921	-538.316245	-307.348467	-232.142576
ΔG (au)	-936.553344	-538.364528	-307.383363	-232.175367

stable fragments are given in this table. As seen in this table, all fragments have negative values. Reaction pathways from O₁ to O₁₅ are estimated through these energy values given in the Table 3.

Conclusions

The molecule was analysed whether stable fractions found through the analysis of bond lengths and angles shown in Table 1 were compatible with electrochemical values found in Table 3. In addition to predicting that the fragmentation occurring from the bond lengths starting from long to short ones, molecules are divided into fractions by electronegative atoms in molecules, bond lengths, bond angles and by taking into consideration the stable-close ring.

When bond angles and bond lengths were investigated, values written bold in Table 1 gave preliminary information about the fragmentation sites of the molecule. Due to the bond angles and bond lengths of bold written values being higher than the others, S₂₂, S₃₀ and O₁₁ were estimated to

be fragmented around S-N, S-C and C-O bonds. According to Fig. 1 of O molecule, O₃, O₃₂, N₃₃ and N₃₅ molecules on the right, O₂₃, O₂₄, N₂₅ and N₂₇ molecules on the left, and O₁₁ in the centre have negative values when their mulliken loads given in Table 2 are analysed. O and N are electronegative atoms. When mulliken loads of O molecule given in Table 2 were analysed, it was determined that N₂₇ and N₃₅ were atoms with the highest electronegativity. Electronegativity ranking continued as N₃₃, O₁₁, N₂₅, O₂₃, O₃₁, O₃₂, O₂₄ atoms respectively. Various fractions were obtained by fragmentation from bonds close to these atoms. N₂₇ and N₃₅ in Table 2 are the atoms with the lowest mulliken load on their O molecule. Therefore, the fragmentation process was started from these atoms. First, several variations of fragmentation from the N atoms at the terminal points were experimented.

For each fraction, electrochemical calculations within gaseous phase were analysed. ΔE energy, ΔH enthalpy and ΔG Gibbs free energy values given in Table 3 are stated for

each fragment separately. When ΔG Gibbs free values were analysed, it was seen that ΔG value of each fragmentation was negative. These results show that fragmentation occurred spontaneously. Fragments with the lowest electrochemical energy, in other words, the most stable fragments are O_1 with -1801.392479 au, O_3 with -1746.097532 au, and O_2 with 1746.043727 au, and O_4 with -1690.748730 au respectively.

The probable stable fragmentation pathway of O molecule is given in Fig. 2. In these probable pathways, fragmentation process was carried out from different electronegative parts of the molecule, and thermochemical values in each fragmentation were calculated. In these possible fragmentation pathways, OBSH molecule was fragmented into its smallest fragment; thus the fate of OBSH in nature was determined for further experimental studies.

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